

Street Children and the Importance of Education

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Abstract

Street children, who are they? What level of education do they have? Can they be properly educated? Are they interested in school? These questions are convoluted and challenging to address. On one hand, there is the conviction that education forms an integral component in the lives of children. On the other hand, many street children cannot avail themselves of this privilege. For street children, survival on the streets is their sole priority and trying to get an education is often suspended. Thus, many of them are caught in this great predicament. The lives of street children are complex to comprehend. It is also perplexing to try to understand how they survive on the streets with limited or no education. It is against this background that this non-empirical research was written. The principal objective was to try to ascertain why these children do not attend school. With the analysis of existing literature, it tried to offer a definition of street children and described life on the streets. It also presented a clear understanding about some of the characteristics of street children. It further investigated the issues that surround street children and education.

Keywords: street children, street life, education

1. Introduction

The number of street children is increasing at a startling rate. Although this phenomenon is relatively new and there is a paucity of information. It is thought-provoking to know that because they are often considered in a purely negative manner many people also treat them with apathy, indifference, and disinterest. This predicament further exacerbates the situation and makes it almost inconceivable to view them in the positive. It is also abstruse to grasp comprehend the way they live on the streets. With the analysis of current literature this paper examined their lifestyle as it relates to education. It offered possible definitions and demonstrated how street children are always portrayed in an unfavorable manner. This paper presented an objective and informed perspective of the lifestyle of street children and did not conjure sensationalism. It is the firm opinion that if people are more knowledgeable about the way street children live, they may be more understanding about their trials and tribulations and may demonstrate more concern and support for these children to be properly educated.

2. Definition of street children

It is intricate and perplexing to accurately formulate a single definition for street children because this phenomenon is relatively new and convoluted to grasp. In addition, nearly every country views them in different ways. A review of the literature demonstrated that they are portrayed in a totally unimaginable manner. Consortium For Children Street (2021) depicted them as an invisible population in the

world. They are overlooked by religious organizations, government officials, law and policymakers and many others in society. Rr *et al.* (2021) claimed that street children are regarded as trash, because they cause public unrest by their unruly conduct. They also held the firm view that street children regularly experience various types of exclusion, discrimination, and exploitation in the social, political, intellectual, religious sphere of life. Reza and Henly (2018) ^[35] posited that street life is utterly unbearable and totally unacceptable. They believed that life on the streets is continually, marred with filth, disease, violence, and poverty and there, these children battle for survival. Kwaku (2019) ^[21] believed that because the street is their dwelling place they struggle and battle there for survival. Similarly, Atwar and Engkus (2020) ^[4] stated that because street children are connected and identified with uproar, upheaval, hideous crime they are considered a social outcast. On the streets they are socially susceptible and vulnerable to the environment. Irawati *et al.* (2021) ^[15] opined that street children have minimal support from family and significant others. They work on the streets and undesirable places like under bridges parking lots and vacant land. Mulekya *et al.* (2021) ^[25] merely defined them as individuals who literally inhabit the streets. Sanjay *et al.* (2019) ^[38] categorically mentioned that they are constantly at high risk. They are unprotected and defenceless. They are exposed to multitudinous types of exploitation, abuse and illnesses. They are deprived and stripped of their rights. They are disregarded and rejected by society. Their childhood is even taken away. They are deprived of

everything, and their lives are always in jeopardy. Sanjay *et al.* (2019)^[38] also claimed that these children need proper guidance and direction. Their only goal and aspiration are to seek the basics on the streets. With little education their future is wretched and miserable. Ismael (2019)^[16] conducted research among street children in Baqubah. He gave countless reasons for the presence of children on the streets. Some of them included the loss of parents or significant others and disintegration of family. Others were extreme poverty, use of illicit drug abuse in the homes and excessive domestic violence. He further stated that some adults literally send their children to beg on the streets. Societal *et al.* (2021)^[41] also agreed that inordinate poverty and lack of parental guidance encourage children to live on the streets.

Consortium for Street Children (2019) noted that although many people use the terms “street children” and “homeless children” interchangeably they are not synonymous. They opined that there are some differences because not all street children are homeless. Consortium for Street Children (2019) explained that some street children seek refuge and accommodation at drop-in centres and half-way houses. Thus, children who are considered street children are not necessarily homeless. They toil, recreate, and spend time on the street, but return to their family.

A review of the literature described street children in a completely undesirable and distasteful manner. The research findings by Prasad (2021)^[31] posited that more than a third of the street children claimed that they chose to live on the streets because they were deprived of the affection from their family. As a result, they were disillusioned and distrustful of new acquaintances. Even the efforts to rehabilitate them by non-governmental institutions were seemingly impossible. As a result of this great mistrust that they have for others Prasad (2021)^[31] further stated that these children may circumvent issues before they reveal the whole truth. Hence, this type of behaviour often compounds their ability to succeed in education. This eccentric and unconventional background makes the teaching and learning almost impossible to achieve.

Dutta (2018)^[10] held the firm view that life on the streets is a constant challenge for survival. Although they live in the major city, they are unable to take full advantage of the comforts of urban life. Pratap and Singh (2021)^[32] believed that street children are present in several parts of the developing world. They further suggested that because they are not properly protected and supervised by adults they often end up on the streets. As discussed above they do not trust adults and hence their chances of attending school are further minimized.

Pratap and Singh (2021)^[32] claimed that the life of street children in Botswana and India was quite disturbing and added that it is not uncommon to see street children wandering the streets in search of essential necessities like food, water, clothing, and shelter. Their battle for survival is unceasing. In addition to neglect and exploitation they are also prone to gang violence and physical and sexual abuse. It is not surprising that they are recruited by drug dealers and sex-traffickers and many of them are forced into prostitution, (Parveen 2019)^[30]. It is within this austere and grim scenario issues like education are almost non-existent and unattainable for several street children. Pratap and

Singh (2021)^[32] found that many of the street children have little formal education and are dropouts of school. However, it follows that when these same children become adults there are literally no jobs available for them and thus, they return to the streets often as delinquents and criminals.

3. Life on the streets

The various definitions mentioned above presented an unambiguous idea of the rigors and horrors that street children endure daily. Lucas (2022)^[22] posited that street children experience tremendous difficulty to survive on the streets. Taib *et al.* (2022)^[42] believed that the problem of street children is societal and thus, governments and families are required to address this social ill. They further stated that street children, because of their rambunctious behaviour cause unrest in the community. They regularly disturb the peace and order of the city. This phenomenon becomes more convoluted to grasp what these children endure on the streets. It ought to be borne in mind that the word “street” forms an intrinsic component of life of street children. It is their world. It is their environment. It is a way of life. It is what they know. It is on the streets their needs are met. It is on the streets they eat, sleep, shelter and play. Aptekar and Stoecklin (2014)^[3] stated that it is their abode. They further explained that street children survive, socialize and hence, establish friendship on the streets. A review of the literature, Makofane (2014)^[23], Nega *et al.* (2021)^[27], (Reza and Bromfield 2019)^[34], Stephen *et al.* (2016)^[40] also recognised this plight. They stated that street children are always associated with acts of violence, heinous crime, and social disturbances. Hasrianti *et al.* (2022)^[17] also believed that the violence that street children received by parents is a factor that caused them to live on the streets. Yahya (2018)^[46] posited that it is not uncommon to find street children in railway and bus terminals begging for assistance and essential necessities. Some of them frequent clubs and are engaged in prostitution. They usually work in unfit and dangerous conditions and their health is always compromised. On the streets these children become socially susceptible and vulnerable to their environment. This scenario does not foster education neither is apt for teaching and learning. What options do street children have to learn? How can they be taught? How can the teaching and learning be made available to them? The answers are not so simple. The United Nations (2017)^[45] declared the number of street children is increasing rapidly. Darragh (2019)^[8] mentioned that street children are always subjected to violence and abuse. Research conducted in Bangladesh by Reza and Bromfield (2019)^[34] revealed that street children are always taken advantage of. They are exposed to multiple types of abuse and are forced into sexual exploitation. It is instructive to note that street children are stripped of the all luxury, comfort and security that a stable home provides. They sleep in deserted and derelict places. Some even live in bus terminals, railway stations and under bridges. These places lack basic hygiene and are riddled with rodents and other harmful animals that bring disease. Further, these children drink water that is not portable and eat food that is sometimes spoilt. The girls are utterly defenseless and weak. To muster courage, boost their esteem, eke a living they sleep with various persons. This type of undesirable behaviour, though shocking and repulsive only exacerbates

the scenario and makes them more susceptible to further abuse, (Okoeguale *et al.* 2020) ^[28]. In this way, the phenomenon of street remains a big issue, and according to Irawati *et al.* (2021) ^[15], this atrocious and brutal cycle continues to deteriorate, and street children suffer exceedingly.

These children lack adult supervision and are repeatedly subjected to psychosocial, emotional, and social problems. They have low self-esteem and feel inferior. They are also likely to contract transmittable and infectious illness. Kwaku (2019) ^[21] conducted research in Accra and claimed that street children work mainly as porters and sex workers. These unlawful activities further expose them to great peril. Therefore, it is abundantly explicit that they are more prone to violence, sexual abuse, and physical and psychological harm. Life on the streets is miserable, exacting, and onerous. Many of them toil under extremely perilous conditions to eke out a living. Some of them sell stolen goods and beg for pittance at traffic intersections. Life is so bitter, unbearable, and grim that some of them ultimately exchange sex for money.

Street children are defenceless, unprotected and live in peril, but they do have some coping skill to eke out a living. Makofane (2014) ^[23] described them as resourceful and cunning. Kwaku (2019) ^[21] also believed that they are resilience and always devise ways to cope with adversity. For example, they are aware of the various religious and cultural events and often frequent those places only to benefit from almsgiving or whatever is distributed. They also benefit from the various NGOs and charitable organizations. The literature presented street children in diverse ways, but (Derivois *et al.* 2019) ^[9] (Raju and Sharmin 2016) ^[33], (Scheper-Hughes and Hoffman, 2016) ^[39] suggested that they basically fall into two main categories. They are: children “on” the streets and children “of” the streets.

4. Children “on” the Streets

(Aptekar and Stoecklin 2014) ^[3], (Scheper-Hughes and Hoffman, 2016) ^[39] hypothesized that children “on” the streets work exceptionally hard to eke out a living. They toil daily in the cold, rain, and heat and under arduous conditions to simply support themselves and their families. Some of them are in communication with their families. Some return home periodically after working on the streets. Others return intermittently to a drop-in centre. Children “on” the streets are slavish and submissive. They have minimal education and poor working skills. Hence, they perform menial tasks and receive a pittance. They clean shops, supermarkets, pharmacies, and stores. They sell newspapers or snacks. They wash vehicles. They work in mechanic shops, stores, or groceries. Their pay is obviously insufficient and cannot meet their expenses. Some of them supplement their meager income and indulge in illegal pursuit such as drugs and prostitution. Julien (2022) ^[20] posited that because they are involved in such unlawful activities they are repeatedly arrested, beaten, and interrogated by police officers. Children “on” the streets work at a very tender age and very often their education and social life are frequently compromised, suspended, permanently. They work, gain money, and continue to survive on the streets. Thus, education for them is not

essential.

5. Children “of” the Streets

Children “of” the streets are bold and brazen and believe that the streets are their homes. They safeguard and defend what they consider as their territory. They work regularly on the streets, during the day and night. Endris and Sitota (2019) ^[11] stated that they beg for the essentials. They solicit money, food, clothing from the public. Some steal anything, that can make their life more comfortable. Others are involved in prostitution and illegal drugs. Unlike children “on” the streets, they seldom visit their families. They do not even like to speak about them. When they give an account of their lives or speak of their life at home, it is usually delivered in a flippant, melancholy, and dismissive manner. It is interesting to mention that children “of” the streets are usually more aggressive and more violent than children “on” the streets.

As a collective group, children “on” and “of” the streets customarily begin the day very early, about 05.00 a.m. Those who work during the night begin at around 10.00 a.m. This schedule is flexible and unplanned, (Julien (2022) ^[20]. Children “on” or “of” the streets constantly endure the hardships of life. Survival on the streets is of paramount significance. Consequently, street children do whatever it takes to live. According to the Literature, (Derivois *et al.* 2019) ^[9], (Hills *et al.* 2016) ^[19], some of them sell whatever they can find. Some even sell themselves.

Because most of them live in deteriorating physical environments like marketplaces, bus stations, rum shops, busy streets, and traffic intersections, they are susceptible to several risks. Apart from enduring hunger, they are also exposed to social, psychological, and mental hazards. Thus, according to the Literature (Aptekar and Stoecklin 2014) ^[3], (Scheper-Hughes and Hoffman, 2016) ^[39] the streets form an indispensable component of their lives. It is on the streets that they satisfy their basic needs for: food, water, clothing, and shelter. In addition, they earn a living on the streets. This is the harsh reality. It is wretched and deprived, but it is the home for street children. This atrocious and brutal cycle continues. These children who experience abuse and rejection at home literally embrace a similar practice on the streets.

The definitions noted above stated that the public view street children from different perspectives. They also formulate an opinion of who they are. Some assume that these children do not avail themselves of the various opportunities, but deliberately choose to live on the streets. Julien (2022) ^[20] hypothesized that those who have a deep sense compassionate, and understanding may inadvertently contribute to the presence of street children. This arises in cases where when street children are very young. For example, little children about five or six years old, who routinely solicit funds on the streets often look unthreatening, powerless and inoffensive. These street children may adjure and procure funds with minimal effort. Their parents are elated and have little or no hesitancy, in encouraging and promoting this type of inappropriate behaviour. When these same little children develop physically and show tangible signs of maturity, a totally different scenario occurs, (Julien 2022) ^[20]. They are often expelled and pushed away in a hostile and inhumane manner

because they occupy public space. They become a nuisance as they continue to mature. They are very often rebuffed and discarded, and this makes begging and vending even more convoluted.

Julien (2022) ^[20] further indicted that some street children are also defenseless to pressures and demands from drug dealers, pimps, criminals, and pornographers. These people manipulate leverage and sexually exploit these children. They promise them money, food, clothing and shelter. The glamour of gaining money is very attractive and enticing, they accede and yield to illegal practices. This deadly cycle continues. In return for favours received, they are forced to follow all the dictates and commands of their new owners. Consequently, they become involved in all sorts of illegal practices like burglary, prostitution, selling drugs, and performing lewd acts, (Julien 2022) ^[20]. To further escalate this situation, most of them have little or no educational opportunities and are conceivably illiterate. This scenario is certainly not apt for education. What options do street children have to learn? The answers are not so simple.

6. Sniffing Glue to Survive

According to the literature street children beg to eke out a living. Others work to support themselves and their family. Still, some engage in illegal activities. On the other hand, there are those who turn to other illicit and harmful substances as a means of dealing with the hunger, thirst, and discontent that they encounter daily on the streets. Yahya (2018) ^[46] claimed that street children turn to drugs for several reasons. Some of them do not trust adults and are afraid to share their problems with them. They do not want to be punished or be rejected by adults. They refuse to seek assistance and because of ignorance they turn to a life of drugs on the streets. Many children use drugs because they believe that it helps to stimulate the brain and produces results. It also alleviates anxiety and fosters happiness and joy enjoy, (Yahya 2018) ^[46]. Street children engage in drugs abuse because of negative peer influence and the need to be recognized and accepted by others. Some indulge in drugs because there is no supervision from parents and adults. Others claim that it fortifies them with the boldness to withstand the violence on the streets.

Many street children use solvent-based glue to reduce the pangs of hunger. Some of them use it to relieve themselves of the cold temperature and grapple with angst and dissatisfaction. This illicit substance also gives them the audacity to steal and engage in survival sex. It is a pragmatic response to a life which is characterized by anguish and despondency. Sanjay *et al.* (2019) ^[38] explained that drug and solvent abuse is widespread and is used as an escape from the reality of daily life and many children are forced to turn to crime to survive. The use of glue keeps children attracted to the streets. They become addicted to the glue, but the use of this substance causes a change in their personalities and most of them turn very antagonistic and confrontational with one another and members of the public. Sanjay *et al.* (2019) ^[38] believed that although the use of solvent-based glue may render some measure of comfort to street children, it has adverse social effects and deleterious physiological consequences. Sanjay *et al.* (2019) ^[38] also added that the persistent use of solvent-based glue can damage the liver, lungs and brain and can ultimately

lead to sudden death.

Sanjay *et al.* (2019) ^[38] explained that the term “inhalant” refers to a variety of household and commercial products that are legally available. They include volatile solvents such as gasoline, glue, paint and polishes, anesthetics such as chloroform, ethers and nitrous oxide, nitrates and aerosols. These products can be inhaled deliberately into the system by sniffing or huffing. The chemicals found in inhalants are as varied as their use. Cigarette lighters and refills contain the gas butane. Paint thinner may have toluene, turpentine ethyl acetate or mineral spirits. Fingernail polish remover and rubber cement contain acetone. Pressurized cans of hair spray, computer cleaners and whipped cream contain fluorinated hydrocarbons. Medical anesthetic gases contain either chloroform, halothane, or nitrous oxide, and are also known as “laughing gas.” Thus far, with the use of literature, definitions of street children were offered. In addition, street life was explained, and it demonstrated that education does not have a priority. Nonetheless, this next portion looks at the importance of education and the barriers that hinder street children from gaining access.

7. Importance of education

Cahyani *et al.* (2021) ^[5] held the firm view that education is necessary for proper survival. They believed that it allows persons to maximize their potential and thus, achieve their goals and aspirations. Cahyani *et al.* (2021) ^[5] further added that inclusive education ought to be meet the needs of all students even street children. They contended that initially many people thought that inclusive education only included children with special needs or those who need special education. However, inclusive education must also cater to the needs of street children. This means it must value, appreciate and recognize that all children can learn. Hasan *et al.* (2022) ^[18] claimed that education is fundamental and ought to be compulsory for all even street children.

Consortium For Children Street (2021) also implied that inclusive education is imperative. This organisation wants to change the world for street children by ensuring they have the same access to services, resources, care, and opportunities like other children. that other children have. They firmly advocated that this can be achieved when people listen carefully to the voices of street children. Furthermore, the public must be willing to put an end the discrimination that street children encounter daily.

Although the views presented by the various authors have merit many street children are unable to embrace this priceless opportunity. Edinyang *et al.* (2020) ^[12] firmly advocated that the involvement of parents and significant others is crucial in the educational life of street children. Anthony and James (2019) ^[2] opined that it is incumbent that policy makers and those interested in education seek measures to properly educate street children. Edmonds *et al.* (2022) ^[13] conducted extensive work in Jinja, Uganda and strongly suggested that it is imperative that education be child-centred and recognize the potentials of all students even street children. Based on her programme she strongly advocated that those interested could be involved in Street Work. This includes counselling, caring, and skills development to help street children reintegrate with their families and avail themselves of the official education

system. She further posited that Street Work is child-centred and incorporates the interest of the students. This encompasses problem solving, self-regulation, a good sense of humour, tenacity, and sound social skills which contribute to their individual resilience. Moreover, it incorporates a deep appreciation and recognition of the wider community which can support the education and the overall well-being of street children. This concept of educating street children is very convoluted and intricate. Life on the streets presents many hindrances and obstacles. It does not encourage learning and thus, it severely hampers the entire teaching and learning process.

8. Obstacles to education

UNICEF (2021) ^[44] stated that about 258 million children experience difficulties in trying to gain proper education and this is largely due to poverty. The International Labour Office (2019) stated that more than one third of all children who engage in child labour is excluded from school. This is quite alarming when one considers that education is important. Titi and Ika (2022) ^[43] stated that street children form part of the less fortunate in society and they experience many difficulties in psychosocial, emotional, and intellectual development aspects. The research findings by Prasad (2021) ^[31] and Dutta (2018) ^[10] clearly demonstrated that trying to educate street children is convoluted. In the first place most of the educators lack proper working facilities and equipment that foster the teaching and learning process. Prasad (2021) ^[31] also highlighted that children are given clothes and school uniforms once a year, but these clothes are very cheap and do not last and some of the children do not even get the correct sizes. Thus, there is a marked difference in appearance between street children and other students. To compound this this scenario, Dutta (2018) ^[10] stated that street children look for every excuse not to attend school. Even while they are at school they need to be constantly supervised and heavily monitored. When this surveillance is absent, they often forget about school and return to the streets. Thus, it is a perpetual battle to keep them in schools.

Pratap and Singh (2021) ^[32] conducted research in certain areas of Botswana and India. Based on various reports they also concluded street children in both Botswana and India have exceedingly low standard of education. Their reports revealed that many boys never attended school or had dropped out of primary school. Moreover, many of the children admitted that they had never attended school or dropped out after primary school, (Hasan, *et al.* 2022) ^[18]. They were totally unaware of the various programmes and assistance offered by the government because they are always preoccupied with survival. This convoluted scenario is further compounded and cemented by the following: high cost of education, lack of motivation and encouragement by parents and significant others insufficient places in schools, and the high cost of living. When added together these issues do not enhance the teaching and learning process nor make studies a priority. Taib *et al.* (2022) ^[42] also found that street children felt they could not achieve their goals or fulfil their aspirations because they left school early and did not have good grades to pursue further education. This lack of adequate education made it exceedingly difficult for them to also acquire proper jobs and thus have a better quality and

standard of life.

Adama (2019) ^[1] conducted research in Kenya and noted that efforts to properly rehabilitate and educate street children failed. Some of the reasons presented were insufficient funds, lack of land, delays in the placement of graduates and lack of public and government support. Adama (2019) ^[1] further mentioned that because there was improper co-ordination among the NGOs themselves and the government it exacerbated the process.

9. Conclusion

It is complicated and intricate to formulate and craft a clear definition of street children. It is also challenging to think about and view these children in a positive light. Nonetheless, with the use of current literature this paper presented some the facts that surround their lives. It also tried to demystify the negative concept that some people have about street children. It carefully examined the two essential categories under which some street children are usually classified: children “on” and children “of” the streets. This paper carefully highlighted some of the woes that children endure on the streets. They are toiling, soliciting, selling, using unlawful and harmful drugs, prostitution and sniffing inhalants or glue. In this way it provided an unambiguous understanding of how street children live. It further presented some of the social conditions that affected the lives of street children and demonstrated that education is not a priority for them. It is the sincere hope that this paper will invigorate minds so that all can be fully cognizant that children are a potent source of hope and aspiration. They form a vital component of society. It is also firmly believed that all children can learn, and it is imperative that they are equipped for learning. Cognition is of paramount significance since it provides the foundation for life and the world of work. Keeping this perspective carefully in mind, listed below are some recommendations that could definitely foster and assist the teaching and learning of these children.

10. Recommendations

To ameliorate the education standard of street children it is highly recommended that:

11. Parents should

1. Begin to build rapport with their children, become passionately involved in their entire life, supervise, and monitor their studies and their work.
2. Continuously engage their children in open discussions to be currently informed as to what is affecting them and share with them the negatives that hinder their education.
3. Regularly and consistently support their children to develop strong and positive personalities, resistant skills, and solid techniques in achieving solid self-esteem.

12. Community

1. Need to appreciate, value, and support the efforts of street children.
2. Continue to underscore the significance of education and create an awareness that eliminates discrimination.
3. Ought to dialogue meaningfully with street children to

build the necessary bonds which inculcate values and morals and principles.

Government

1. Continue to provide adequate and regular fund for education and create an awareness about the great value of education.
2. Support the reunification of street children with their families and create more opportunities for street children to return to school.
3. Enforce the laws so that all can avail themselves of education.

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